

live larvae/tiller, compared with 0-1 (mean 0.4) live larva/ tiller in check plots.

The increased carryover of larvae with zero-tillage wheat could be a

factor limiting the next year's rice crop, if nurseries are planted before 20 May. Zero-tillage wheat is safe to grow because *Scirpophaga* do not feed on wheat. *Sesamia inferens* (Wlk.) and

S. uniformis (Dudgn.) have been reported to attack rice and wheat in small numbers, but they could not be detected during this study. □

Rice-based cropping systems under irrigation in North India

P.C. Kharwara, P.K. Sharma, and L.N. Singh, Regional Research Station, Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishva Vidyalaya, Dhaulakuan, Dist. Sirmur (HP), India

Rice is becoming a more important crop during the Jun-Oct monsoon season in irrigated areas of North India because of its higher yield potential and better market price. It has even replaced maize in areas where soils are coarse textured with high permeability. We evaluated rice-based cropping systems for those areas.

A 1983-86 field trial included 9 crops fitted into 7 crop rotations: four 1-yr and three 2-yr. Soil was well-drained (saturated hydraulic conductivity 1 cm/h) sandy loam

Rice-equivalent yields and net returns from rice-based cropping systems evaluated in North India, 1983-86.

Rotation	Rice-equivalent grain yield (t/ha per yr)	Net return (\$/ha per yr)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice - wheat ^a	9.9	500.00	1.22
Rice - linseed - black gram ^a	8.3	423.00	0.98
Rice - toria - wheat - black gram ^a	12.3	491.30	0.77
Rice - linseed - maize (fodder) ^a	10.8	532.50	1.28
Rice - sugarcane + wheat - potato - green gram ^b	13.1	413.90	0.53
Rice - toria - sugarcane - wheat - black gram ^b	10.2	416.70	0.80
Rice - wheat - sugarcane - potato - black gram ^b	15.4	524.20	0.59
CD (5%)	1.0	50.90	—

^aOne-year crop rotation. ^bTwo-year crop rotation.

(Fluvent) with neutral soil reaction and medium soil fertility.

A 2-yr rotation of rice - wheat - sugarcane - potato - black gram gave the highest rice-equivalent grain yield; rice - linseed - black gram gave the lowest (see table). Rice - wheat, the most popular crop rotation of the area, was next to last in grain production. The best 1-yr crop

rotation was rice - toria - wheat - black gram.

Rice - linseed - maize (fodder) gave the highest net returns, equal to rice - wheat, rice - toria - wheat - black gram, and rice - wheat - sugarcane - potato - black gram. The highest benefit-cost ratio was with rice - linseed - maize (fodder), followed by that with rice - wheat. □

ERRATA

D.K. Kundu, F.N. Ponnampereuma, and H.U. Neue. An improved method of representative sampling from aerobic soil solutions. 11 (6) (Dec 1986), 35-36.

The corrected article is reprinted below.

An improved method of sampling representative solutions from aerobic soils

D.K. Kundu, F.N. Ponnampereuma, and H. U. Neue, Soil Chemistry Department, IRRRI

Analysis of a solution collected in situ from aerobic soil can be used for characterizing the soil chemical

environment of upland rice. However, it is difficult to obtain samples from aerobic soils with moisture contents near field capacity (FC). The displacement method for well-packed FC moist soil columns has not been tested for validity under normal pot culture conditions. We evaluated samples collected by the conventional displacement method from three FC moist potted soils with different hydraulic conductivities.

Twelve kilograms each of air-dried (>2 mm sized) Luisiana clay, Maahas clay, and Pila loam soils were placed in 16-liter porcelain pots fitted at the bottom with drainage (coarse sintered glass) tubes. The soils were brought to FC moisture using tensiometers.

To collect soil solutions, 0.5% KSCN as displacing liquid was poured on the soil surfaces. The displaced solutions were drained into measuring cylinders. We tested the collected solutions for SCN-ion at regular intervals. Drops of acidic FeCl₃ solution were used as the indicator (a blood red-colored complex is formed).

From the fast-draining Luisiana clay and Pila loam soils, we could collect only 20-30 ml of soil solution. Beyond this volume, the leachate was diluted by the displacing liquid. In slow-draining Maahas clay, no displacement appeared in the first 200 ml. About 175 ml of soil solution is needed for a complete analysis; the displacement method was not appropriate for soils

with fast drainage properties.

In a second experiment, we compared soil solution collected by the displacement method with equilibrated saturation extracts of three soils.

Equilibrium was ensured by recycling the saturation extracts three times.

Saturating an FC moist soil, then immediately draining it does not give equilibrium extract. Allowing FC moist soils to remain saturated for a long time (beyond 8 h in many cases) might cause soil reduction.

We used three soils set up as in the first experiment, replicated six times. Demineralized water, in volumes required to bring the FC moist soils to saturation, was poured on the soil surface. The first 125-ml leachates were collected as the displaced solutions, and the rest as saturation extract.

The extracts were then recycled

Comparison of pH and Eh values^a of solutions from FC moist soils collected by 2 different methods.

Soil	Soil pH (1:1)	pH		Eh (V)	
		Displaced solution	Recycled saturation extract	Displaced solution	Recycled saturation extract
Luisiana clay	4.1	4.6 a	4.5 b	0.31 b	0.32 a
UK-1 clay loam	6.6	5.9 b	6.5 a	0.29 a	0.26 b
Pila loam	1.5	6.9 b	7.3 a	0.21 a	0.23 b

^a Mean of 6 replications. In a row, treatment means of a given parameter having a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at 5% level.

through soils three times, first allowing them to remain in contact with soil for about 30 min by keeping the drain tube closed. The final (fourth) extract was collected as the equilibrated saturation extract. To prevent further oxidation, the soil solutions were collected in flasks prefilled with N₂ gas.

We measured solution pH and Eh in an electrometric cell under N₂

environment. The recycled saturation extracts were representative of soil solutions; the displaced solutions were seriously diluted and altered by the displacing liquid (demineralized water, pH 5.38) (see table).

During subsequent experiments, we observed that it is necessary to recycle the saturation extract three times in fast-draining soils; recycling once or twice seldom ensured equilibrium. □

R.D. Daquioag, P.O. Cabauatan, and H. Hibino. Balimau Putih. Cultivar tolerant of rice tungro-associated viruses. 11 (6) (Dec 1986), 8.

Please replace the printed table with the corrected copy given here.

Reaction of Balimau Putih and TNI in RTBV and RTSV by test tube inoculation of RTBV and RTSV at 5 insects^a per seedling. IRRI, 1986.

Variety	Plants (no.) infected with ^b			Healthy plants (no.)	Infection (%)	Height reduction (%)		Yield reduction (%)	
	RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV	RTSV			RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV	RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV
TNI	87	31	0	8	93.6	41.6	21.3	90.0	50.0
Balimau Putih	46	68	3	5	95.9	11.4	5.0	18.4	7.6

^a Green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* were given 4 d access to TNI plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV. ^b Total of 4 trials. Detected by ELISA.

Announcements

Spanish translation released

The Spanish edition of *A methodology for on-farm cropping systems research* by H.G. Zandstra, E.C. Price, J.A. Litsinger, and R.A. Morris has been released. The International Development Research Centre of Canada translated and published the edition in cooperation with IRRI. IDRC has distributed copies of the book to all Latin American agricultural libraries on the IRRI

mailing list. Copies also may be ordered from IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. Price is US\$5 LDC and US\$16.70 HDC.

Book on nitrogen in flooded soils published

Recent findings from basic studies on N transformation processes and technology development are summarized and updated in *Nitrogen economy flooded rice soils*,

published July 1986 by Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, The Netherlands. IRRI Agronomist S.K. De Datta was co-editor with W.H. Patrick, Jr.

Rice commonly utilizes less than 40% of applied fertilizer; current studies focus on minimizing N losses and maximizing N use efficiency.

Nitrogen economy flooded rice soils (ISBN 90-247-3361-8) can be ordered from Kluwar Academic Publishers Group, P.O. Box 322, 3300 AH Dordrecht, The Netherlands, at US \$60.50.